

**LABOR EFFICIENCY: THE NEED FOR UNITY OF FACTORS,
METHODS AND TOOLS**

Lobar Anvarova

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ANNOTATION. The article discusses ways to improve labor efficiency and its implementation is an important factor in strengthening the country's economy.

Keywords: labor productivity, actual labor productivity, available labor productivity, potential labor productivity, the impact of reforms on labor productivity, factors that reduce labor productivity, opportunities to increase labor productivity.

Today, the issue of increasing labor efficiency is extremely urgent and necessary. It increases under the influence of a number of factors. For example, rational and productive use of the existing material and technical base and production capabilities, rational organization of the production process on a scientific basis, and increasing the knowledge and skills of employees. Labor efficiency in enterprises and organizations gradually increases in the society where the labor process is organized taking into account these factors. Ignoring these factors and replacing them with repressive or voluntarist methods will have dire consequences. This can be seen in the example of the Soviet experience, which turned to the past at the end of the last century. During the years of Soviet power, for a long period of time, labor efficiency was ensured at the cost of fear, oppression, and forced labor. For example, the establishment of the Belomorkanal, the construction of the Baikal-Amur highway, the development of protected lands - a symbol of the effectiveness of work carried out at the community level, and the completion of five-year plans in four or even three years - were presented as examples of the productivity of the enterprise. In fact, they were all products of labor organized on the basis of the principle of obligation. True, the Soviet government initially tried to organize these events according to the principle of voluntariness. For example, on April 13, 1932, the decision of the government "On the construction of the Baikal-Amur railway" was adopted and its implementation began. The decision envisages attracting the country's citizens to construction in exchange for economic and financial incentives. However, the harsh working conditions in the taiga, the shortage of food products, and the lack of labor tools caused the labor force to flow to other regions.

According to the data, as a result of difficult conditions, in a situation where BAM needed 12 thousand earth diggers, only 504 people worked instead of 2389 drillers, 498 people instead of 5101 carpenters. After that, the government decided to apply the principle of compulsion in the construction of BAM and handed it over to the OGPU (State Department for the Protection of State Security). The administration immediately established the Baikal-Amur camp and in a short period involved 32,411 prisoners in the construction of the highway.

In particular, in the first years of independence, "the following were set as strategic goals in the field of economic reform:

1. Step-by-step formation of a socially oriented market economy, establishment of a powerful and relentlessly developing economic system that increases national wealth and provides necessary conditions for people's lives and activities.

2. Ensuring the protection of private property by the state, which is the basis for creating a multi-level economy, ending the deprivation of property, and developing initiative and perseverance with all measures.

3. Giving wide economic freedoms to enterprises and citizens, abandoning the direct intervention of the state in their economic activities, eliminating the administrative and command methods of managing the economy, wide use of economic factors and incentives.

4. Making deep structural changes in the economy that ensure efficient use of material, natural and labor resources, production of competitive products, joining the world economic system.

5. To form new economic ideas in people, to change their worldview, to enable each person to independently determine the sphere and forms of spending his labor. These measures had a significant impact on the level of labor efficiency in enterprises and organizations. It is for this reason that the country's gross domestic product began to grow, and the volume of production of national economy and industrial products expanded.

In the following years, the reforms carried out within the framework of the Strategy of Actions and the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan gave a tendency to the development of these factors. For example, during the last five years, special attention has been paid to the issues of expanding the non-state sector in the economy, reducing the direct intervention of the state in the activities of enterprises and organizations. As a result, the standard of economic freedom of subjects has increased significantly. Economic freedom, on the one

hand, has led to a sharp increase in the number of entrepreneurship and small business entities. In particular, in 2016, 207 thousand 104 business entities operated in the country, and by 2022 their number will reach 517 thousand 501. On the other hand, thanks to economic freedom, labor efficiency in enterprises and organizations began to increase. Due to the increase in labor productivity, let's say, in 2005, the share of business entities in the gross domestic product of our country was 38.2 percent, and by 2022 this indicator was 51.8 percent. However, it does not follow from this that all measures to reduce the gap between the actual labor efficiency indicator and the cash labor efficiency indicator have been taken in the country's enterprises. There are still a number of problems that hinder the improvement of labor efficiency in the society. For example, it is related to the development of the material and technical base of enterprises and organizations, the diversification of production, the implementation of innovations in production, the organization of the production process on a scientific basis, the reduction of losses during working hours, the improvement of the knowledge and skills of employees, the implementation of a fair remuneration system for labor. issues are waiting for their solution. The successful solution of these issues would have increased the efficiency of work in enterprises and organizations. In conclusion, labor productivity is a powerful factor capable of ensuring sustainable economic development. Large-scale reforms implemented in Uzbekistan during the years of independence created real opportunities for its improvement. The current task is to use these opportunities wisely, and at the same time to take measures to eliminate the factors hindering the increase of labor efficiency.

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